

Mounting Leadership Skills among Young Adults with Disabilities

Ms.G.Ananthi, Dr.Himangshu Das

Assistant Professor, Director NIEPMD & NIEPID,
Department of Special Education,
NIEPMD, Govt. of India, Chennai-603 112, India,

Abstract: A study on 'mounting leadership skills among young adults with disabilities' was carried out with 30 samples. The samples were selected using purposive sampling method, from Colleges and Universities at Tamilnadu. Quasi-Experimental method was followed for the conduct of the study. The independent variables were Age, Type of family and Locality. The dependent variable includes in the study was to incorporate various leadership qualities to the young adults with disabilities especially women. Pre and post-test was conducted using the leadership checklist developed by the investigators. Intervention was given through narration of success stories, oration on recent facilities, current trends and the problems faced by the individual in the society etc, in which the differently abled young adults were made to exhibit and share their ideas through various programs like mono-act, play, drama, and oration of their own experience with the society. Through which the 30 young adults with disabilities were made to express their needs and ideas. This study made everyone to participate and gain skills regarding role of leadership in their life. In this current era even the typical peers has to develop leadership skills for facing the society confidently; in the case of differently abled it is the role of every teacher educators to initiate leadership programs for the differently abled those who are enrolled in higher education. This can be made through various programmes and practices, but the main aim is to make the differently abled more confident on collaring the society and to enhance leadership skills for a better livelihood.

Index Terms -Leadership skills, young adults, livelihood, intervention and success stories.

I.INTRODUCTION

India has the largest population of adolescents in the world being home to 243 million individuals. It has been estimated that estimated 70 million people with disabilities i.e., 5.6 percent of the country's population. In Indian society, there is a deep-rooted social stigma toward body impairment or disfigurement as "inauspicious," thus limiting interaction between people with disabilities and the rest of society. People with disabilities face barriers to education, employment, and public services that could otherwise help them escape poverty. Buildings and transportation are often inaccessible. They also often suffer from social discrimination, stereotypes, and exclusion. As in the general population, there is strong gender and geographic differences among people with disabilities; women and girls in rural areas are often the most disadvantaged. The government has initiated a plethora of programs to promote employment for them, but the impact to date has been negligible. In 2008, for example, the Indian Finance Minister allocated \$360 million for a program to reimburse employers who provide jobs to disabled workers. The aim was to create 100,000 jobs per year, but after three years, the program had generated only 465 jobs. This might be because they lack with prior leadership skills to face the work spot and the society.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study were to mount leadership skills among diffrenly abled young adults with disabilities especially women. The following are the other objectives of the study.

- To identify the young adults with disabilities especially women in higher education.
- To develop various programmes to incorporate leadership skills.
- To develop a checklist for assessing leadership qualities.
- To find out the effectiveness of the programmes conducted for enhancing leadership skills.

- To motivate the teacher educators regarding the various ways to develop self confidence and leadership skills among the disabled community.

1.2 HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

1. There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Age of young adults with disabilities.
2. There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Type of Disability of young adults with disabilities.
3. There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Locality of young adults with disabilities.

1.3 NEED OF THE STUDY

Many parents of youth approaching adulthood worry about their child's future. Whether their child have disabilities or not, parents want to know what they can do to help their sons and daughters decide on a career, support their job hunting, and succeed in the workplace. But parents are unaware of the ways to develop self confidence and incorporate life skills including Leadership skills to fit into a vocational set up and also at any environment for coping their livelihood. Both at home and at college, families and other caring adults play a vital role in helping young people with disabilities to build work skills that will help them successful in employment. Leadership Programme provides disabled people with the skills and confidence to improve their lives and make a difference to the lives of many other disabled people across every sector of society. Thus a need have been roused to find out the various methods for developing Leadership Skills among differently abled especially women perusing their higher education. In this modern world women are exploited more in the society and hence the study was made in mounting programmes for the differently abled adolescent women to improve and enhance their leadership quality and to face the society with courage and confidence.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scopes of the present study are as follows:

1. It makes the individual to believe that they can accomplish anything. Set goals for what you want to do and make a plan to achieve those goals.
2. It creates a peer support network which will help to get connect with other youth leaders with disabilities.
3. It will help them to share their experiences and learn from one another. So that they are getting self motivated and also gains self-confidence in facing hazard situations.
4. Make the individual to become dynamic and also as an active participant in the society to take up challenges.
5. It will help the teacher educators to develop strategies for mounting leadership skills.
6. It provides opportunities to every individual to speak on panels and in front of large groups.
7. It makes the individual to be independent and assertive and also to assume responsibility for taking the steps needed to achieve their goals to become a leader.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A study on Promoting Inter professionalism and Leadership in Disability Studies with Public Health Students from a Family Perspective was conducted by Dana Barber Gonzales (2004) examines the benefits of a Solution Focused Learning (SFL) curriculum for public health students. Inter professional education and leadership training is an integral part of the SFL program. Through the incorporation of families of children with chronic health needs, graduate students receive instruction and practical experience working with a variety of health care disciplines, health administrators, direct service providers, and other representatives of the health system. Another research on Youth Leadership Forums-Providing Leadership Development Opportunities for Youth with Disabilities by Alicia Epstein, et.al by 2006 the Research provides an outline of elements and goals critical to the success of youth development programs. Youth Leadership Forums embody these elements and goals and constitute an important training resource for youth with disabilities. They provide a opportunity for youth to learn and practice leadership skills, discuss issues and ideas with their peers, and learn from successful adult mentors. They also provide a unique opportunity for youth with disabilities to grow, learn, and develop self-advocacy skills that they will need in order to successfully navigate the future. Beside this by 1996 Catalano and Hawkins assessed the effectiveness of 77 youth development programs. Through an extensive review of literature and existing practices, the National Collaborative on Workforce and Disability for Youth (2004) outlined organizational and programmatic components of effective youth programs. Further this study is an innovative approach to incorporate various programmes for the differently in developing Leadership Skills among differently abled.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the quasi-experimental design. This study has only one experimental group and there is no control group. For this study samples are taken from various colleges and universities at Tamilnadu. A total sample of 30 women students with disabilities of higher education made up of 15 between the age 20-25 and 15 others of the age 26-30 participated in the study. These students were expected to have developed an appreciable level of Tamil vocabulary as well as enough listening and comprehension skills, there were about 15 women from solar family and 15 women from nuclear family and the same sample consists of 15 from rural and 15 from urban are of locality. The main independent variables are the age, type of family and locality. The dependent variable includes in the study is to incorporate various leadership qualities to the young adults with disabilities. Pre and post-test was conducted using the checklist developed by the investigators. Intervention was given through narration of success stories, oration on recent facilities, current trend and the problems faced by the individual in the society etc, in which the differently abled young adults were made to exhibit and share their ideas through various programs like mono-act, play, drama, oration of her own experience with the society. Through which the 30 young adults were made to express their needs and ideas. This study ultimately made everyone to participate and gain skills regarding role of leadership in their life. Collected data are analyzed by using small sample t-test and the mean scores were calculated. Individual percentages are obtained and in case summary each students are given with their pre and post-test result and differences. Beside this every individual are instructed to share their experience regarding the programmes.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1

There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Age of young adults with disabilities.

Table no:1

AGE	TEST	MEAN	SD	T- VALUE
20-25	Pretest	14.60	2.06	12.84*
	Posttest	24.13	2.58	

26-30	Pretest	20.33	6.03	1.33*
	Posttest	22.67	3.81	

*significant at 0.05 level.

From the table it has been observed that performance of women belonging to the age group of 26- 30 are significantly higher than women between the age group of 20-25. This might be due to the emotional maturity and the exposure obtained by the individuals. More over the post test result of the individuals is higher than the pretest thus the hypothesis “There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to age” is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Type of Family of young adults with disabilities.

Table no:2

TYPE OF FAMILY	TEST	MEAN	SD	T- VALUE
Solar family	Pretest	17.60	5.64	1.42*
	Posttest	21.13	4.59	
Nuclear family	Pretest	19.47	5.90	1.45*
	Posttest	21.53	4.74	

*significant at 0.05 level.

From the table it has been observed that performance of women belonging to solar family is significantly higher than women belonging to nuclear family. This might be due to the family support given to the individual. More over the post test result of the individuals is higher than the pre test thus the hypothesis “There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to type of family” is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to Locality of young adults with disabilities.

Table no:3

LOCALITY	TEST	MEAN	SD	T- VALUE
Rural	Pretest	18.27	5.41	.85*
	Posttest	20.47	5.26	
Urban	Pretest	21.73	5.24	.27*
	Posttest	21.13	5.15	

*significant at 0.05 level.

From the table it has been observed that performance of women belonging to Urban area is significantly higher than women belonging to the Rural area. This might be due to the environment and the exposure given to them from the society. More over the post test result of the individuals is higher than the pre test thus the hypothesis “There will be no significant difference in the acquisition of leadership skills with respect to locality” is rejected.

V. CONCLUSION

This study mainly aims in bringing out the programmes for developing leadership qualities among differently abled young adult women. Even though if it is a small project it aims for the participation of differently abled in every activities and to develop valuable skills required for enhancing their livelihood. This study mainly benefits the teacher educators to adapt new methods for teaching and developing leadership skills to the differently abled community.

VI. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Research studies in general and experimental studies in particular, have limitations due to many factors. It is the responsibility of the investigator to see that the study is conducted with maximum care in order to be reliable.

- Sample size is less.
- Participants who gave permission for data collection only selected as the sample.
- Profound differently abled sample were excluded from the study.

VII. REFERENCE

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WEB RESOURCE

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<http://www.waisman.wisc.edu/cedd/pdfs/products/community/Leadership.pdf>